

Development of a Cricothyrotomy Education and Training Module: A Delphi Analysis

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Background

- Difficult airway algorithms recommend emergency invasive airway (cricothyrotomy) when clinicians fail to establish adequate oxygenation and ventilation.
- Anesthesia providers infrequently perform cricothyrotomy, potentially leading to patient harm and civil liability.
- There is a lack of effective cricothyrotomy training for anesthesia providers.

Purpose and Aims

- Purpose: Gather expert consensus on failed airway and cricothyrotomy pedagogy to create an outline for a cricothyrotomy education module.
- Aim: Strengthen anesthesia providers' training resources and anesthesia provider confidence in failed airway and cricothyrotomy situations.

Methods

- Delphi analysis with invitations to 45 airway experts in Southern California.
- Experts were anesthesia providers with various backgrounds and education and were selected because of their affiliation with Kaiser Permanente school of Anesthesia.
- 1st round: Survey to determine participant experience with cricothyrotomy and related training.
- 2nd round: Survey to determine important concepts to include in the educational module.
- 3rd round: Virtual meeting via zoom to elaborate on themes.
- Creation of an outline for an education module based on the Delphi method.

Results

Delphi Analysis Round One

- Out of 45 selected participants, 17 completed the survey.

Delphi Analysis Round Two

- Of the 17 participants who participated in round one, 11 participants completed round 2 survey.

Delphi Analysis Round Three

- Four certified registered nurse anesthetists joined the round three zoom meeting.
- Participants reached consensus on module contents.

Themes from Delphi Analysis

Delphi Analysis Question	Most Frequent Answer
Overall theme	Frequent online and simulation training results in providers feeling prepared to perform a cricothyrotomy.
Is Cricothyrotomy education beneficial?	Very beneficial
Which cricothyrotomy technique is preferred?	Wire, Surgical (bougie-assisted), Needle.
How frequently should training occur?	Annually
Best modality for cricothyrotomy education?	Online module; simulation
Barriers to cricothyrotomy education?	Cost, time, access to materials
Include nontechnical skills?	Yes, simulation should include decision point to perform cricothyrotomy.
Include other specialties?	ER Providers

Would you be interested in attending an advanced airway course that was regularly offered, and included hands-on, simulated experience in performing cricothyrotomy?

Educational Modules/Outline

- Introduction to Cricothyrotomy & what to expect from the module
- Cricothyrotomy Procedure
 - Decision making process (Difficult Airway Algorithm)
 - Technique (Needle, Wire-guided, Surgical)
- Discussion of Variables
 - Anesthesia Non-Technical Skills: Communication, leadership, and situational awareness of provider and team members
 - Equipment available in every operating room (scalpel, bougie, ETT)
 - Training options for hands-on exposure and practice

Discussion

- An annual, online module is the most accessible means of cricothyrotomy training for anesthesia providers.
- Providers should be familiar with the equipment available for Cricothyrotomy.
- The stress Anesthesia providers experience when deciding to perform a cricothyrotomy is difficult to replicate.

Limitations

- Small sample Size (n < 30)
- Lacked diversity
 - Only included anesthesia provider responses
- Convenience Sampling

Recommendations

- Develop a cricothyrotomy education and training module from the DNP Project Outline.
- Pilot education & training module at a Southern California medical facility.
- Evaluation of education and training module to assess post-intervention efficacy.

References

